

Finding the Best Methods on People Development at PT Pertamina EP – Sangatta Field

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ABSTRACT: People Development is an important element for a company to survive. It's also implemented at PT Pertamina EP, Zona 9 – Sangatta Field. It can done more effectively and efficient on the result in this research. This research aims to find the best methods in developing people competencies. Based on conceptual framework of People Development, it consists of three main pillars : People, Process, Technology. Each pillar has a specific influence and purpose in realizing an ideal people developments system. By conducting research using qualitative methods, it was found that within each pillar, a specific or main program is needed that has the most impact on the company's progress. Mutation or job rotational replacement has a significant impact on improving company performance through the 'People' aspect. Talent & Matrix Development captures all employee aspirations according to each worker's interests and talents, and determining the appropriate training according to employee needs can enhance worker competencies, thereby advancing the company.

KEYWORDS: Job rotation, People development, Talent development, Trainings.

INTRODUCTION

People development on a company is an important thing that can't be denied as long as those company exist. Eventhough it's just look as a supporting sector doesn't mean it doesn't important. Soft skills and hard skills for employee is one of many succession key for the company to sustain.

Pertamina is a State-Owned Enterprise that run in Energy sector, especially Oil and Gas., it was targeting to produce 1 million BOEPD, in 2025. To reach that target, Pertamina need a competent talent that able to run the company. Pertamina need to develop some programs to improve capabilities, even softskills and hardskills, and also the leadership in Pertamina.

PT Pertamina EP, Zone 9 – Sangatta Field, located in East Kalimantan, and in 2022 it produce oil around 1,800 BOPD and gas around 2,4 MMSCFD. Sangatta Field are lead by a Field Manager. It has 6 divisions on it which consist of 76 workers and many outsources. To reach the target production, Sangatta Field have to develop their employees to be more competent and skillful.

People development in companies is an important things for them to increase the sustainability. Either stakeholder, employees, management, or even the sub-contractor would affect the company sustainability. For that so, people development is a must for every particular member who contribute on the system. People, Process, and Technology were the keys on developing the Knowledge Management. Nowadays, Knowledge Management or we usually called it KM, become one of many to be consider on company strategies. KM not only giving a new learning system or increasing capabilities, but also Employee Quality and Productivity.

The objectives on this topic will focus on completing several objectives on analyzing the option on people development at PT Pertamina EP Zone 9 – Sangatta Field, identify the talent development acceleration mismatches for the employees, and identify the employee needs for the development program to support their career path. Based on the background and business issue that has been describe, we got a few question that relate on People Development. We need to know :

1. What are the best option for people development framework at PT Pertamina EP – Sangatta Field ?
2. What kind of program to accelerate talent development ?
3. What are the best methods in developing employee capabilities or competencies ?

Conceptual Framework & Literature Review

To support business strategy at PT Pertamina EP, some improvement on optimizing human resources would also optimize productivity for the company.

Figure 1.0 People Development Conceptual Framework

The main point in this conceptual framework is the Current Business Situation that focuses on increasing Production, Productivity & Effectiveness, and Revenue or Income for the company. To support those business strategies, companies need people development as a framework to optimize them. There are 3 main factors on people development, such as :

- People
- Process
- Technology

Literature Review

Talent development is about enhancing knowledge, skills, and capabilities of workers. It's a part of the wider concept of talent management, which encompasses the strategies organizations use to recruit, choose, cultivate, and oversee talented staff. (Collings & Mellahi, 2009)

Talent development refers to the systematic process of fostering and enhancing the skills, knowledge, and abilities of employees or individuals within an organization. Its purpose is to ensure that employees can fulfil their current roles effectively, prepare for future roles within the organization, and contribute to the growth and success of the organization.

In some companies, talent development emphasized cultural alignment, while those from multinational companies leaned towards psychological evaluations for talent identification. (Zhang, Y. E., & Nesbit, P. L. 2018). This disparity echoes the idea in literature

that talent definition often depends on the industry of profession. In local companies, emphasizing cultural aspects when identifying talent in company culture. In contrast, multinational companies' reliance on psychological evaluations mirrors their preference for structured human resources management approaches

Despite the differences, human resources leaders from local companies and multinational companies shared a similar philosophy towards talent development (Mahapatra, G. P., & Dash, S. 2022). They usually adopted an exclusive-develop stance on talent development. Associating talent with roughly 15% of their workforce. These employees were then given growth opportunities to prepare for vital future roles. This prevalent viewpoint aligns with western talent development literature (Andre, van Vianen, Jansen, Petrovic & Bunjevac 2019).

Key components of talent development include:

1. **Training Programs:** These are designed to enhance specific skills or knowledge in areas pertinent to an individual's job role. (Martini, S., Khan, W. A., & Muttaqiyathun, A. 2023).
2. **Mentoring and Coaching:** Experienced professionals provide guidance, advice, and support to less experienced employees, helping them navigate their careers and improve their professional abilities (Nazifah, L. 2023)
3. **Leadership Development:** Preparing promising employees for leadership roles within the organization by enhancing their leadership skills and providing them with strategic insights.
4. **Succession Planning:** Identifying and developing employees to fill key business leadership positions in the future.
5. **Performance Management:** Regularly assessing and providing feedback on an employee's performance to ensure alignment with organizational goals and to identify areas for improvement.
6. **Career Development:** Offering opportunities for employees to explore and plan their career paths within the organization.
7. **Continuous Learning Opportunities:** Encouraging and providing resources for employees to pursue further education, certifications, or other learning experiences.

Most effective talent development practice that participants indicated that their organizations had adopted a diverse range of talent development practices. Among these, job-based developmental programs were the most popular and deemed most efficient in terms of cost and performance outcomes. This aligns with western human resources studies that emphasize the importance of hands-on learning and introspection in development.

Overall, talent development aims to retain top talent, increase employee engagement, and promote a culture of continuous growth and improvement within the organization.

i. People

On the pillar of People, it have three aspects. There are Job Assignment, Task Force, and Job Rotational Replacement. Job assignment is about an allocation of specific roles, tasks, can be projects to individuals or team based on various factors that need specific skill, experience or might be even organizational politics. Job assignment usually need a skill matching on its individual to ensure the optimum productivity on it's team or company. Organizational needs also could be a consideration to reach the short-term and long-term goals. In a few companies, assignments may be used as strategic tools for business expansion and canvassing to new market.

A Task Force or special work assignment in a dedicated team is established to address a specific condition or problem. Typically, a task force team is formed abruptly to resolve the issue quickly, allowing them to find the root cause of the problem, seek the best solutions, and implement them. The task force team usually continues to operate until they achieve significant results or changes. Often, the task force team requires specific skills and experience to address the problem and conditions being faced.

Position rotation is very important in a company. Its primary purpose is to fill competencies and gaps in vacant positions. Usually, job rotation is accompanied by job promotions or individual promotions. The goal of job rotation is also to enable workers to acquire a broader helicopter view. Gaining new knowledge and challenges can increase the work enthusiasm of the employees. Being in a new work environment with a different atmosphere also has an impact on the mental health of the workers.

ii. Process

On the pillar of Process, it have three aspects too. There are Internal Job Posting, Knowledge Sharing, and Talent & Development Matrix. The Human Capital division usually conducts an Internal Job Posting program to fill vacant positions. This is often used as

a stepping stone for workers who have competent and above-average skills. Internal Job Posting is announced within the internal environment of the company to gather the interest of employees who are enthusiastic about accelerating their career journey.

The importance of knowledge sharing in a company lies in its role as a medium and tool for human resource development, building a productive culture, and playing a crucial part in supporting the business strategy of the company. In some companies, this activity might be perceived as merely adding to and burdening the company's costs. However, this is a misconception. By improving the quality of human resources, one way of which is through knowledge sharing activities, it is essentially the same as the company investing in its workforce, enabling the workers to yield greater results for the company. This support is what helps the company to enhance the quality of its human resources.

Talent & development matrix must be structured according to the needs of the company. The matrix for both the organization and the individual is clearly defined in a 'Code of Conduct,' which encompasses aspects of the AKHLAK values. The designed talent & development matrix must be relevant to the goals or KPIs of each individual or institution. This matrix also serves as a reference for workers in achieving their rights within the company. Here, 'rights' refer to each individual's entitlement to receive relevant training, assignments, or activities that support the company's operations, as well as the determination of a career path for each worker.

iii. Technologies

On this pillar of technologies, it also have three aspects. There are, Soft & Hard Skill Trainings, Sharing Information, and Upgrading Technologies. Continuing from the previous explanation, hard skill training is a right for every worker and an obligation of the company to fulfill and enhance the quality of human resources in accordance with the company's expectations. As time progresses, the equipment used will inevitably evolve and change. To master the use of the latest equipment, refreshment training and introduction to new tools are necessary. This is where hard skill training becomes very important for the company. Hard skill training can be conducted through simulator tests or direct equipment operation, taking into account a controlled system and prioritizing HSSE (Health, Safety, Security, and Environment) aspects. With the implementation of this hard skill training, it is expected that the human resources will understand the intricacies and capacities of the tools used. Not only that, but they will also learn how to resolve issues or troubleshoot problems that may arise with the equipment.

Not much different from knowledge sharing, what distinguishes this information sharing activity is that it is limited to a platform provided by the ICT team. Here, users (human resources) can access, download, and upload problems and experiences they have encountered. This platform can also serve as a medium for discussion, enabling users to find solutions to existing problems. Technological Updating, as time progresses, the technology used becomes more advanced. The hope is to achieve higher and more precise production outcomes than before, thereby increasing the company's revenue. It's not just about boosting revenue, but also the expectation that with the use of the latest technology, there will be fewer problems arising.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative methodology. By using qualitative methods in research, it would provide insight into the problem to develop ideas for potential quantitative research. Most of qualitative research on getting high quality data is by doing some interviews which might be structured, semi-structured on unstructured. We also could use some group discussion, observations, or any other methods to get high quality data.

This final project collects data on multiple sources, includes procedures, interviews, documentation and any other reports.

Bloom's Taxonomy

There are 6 levels of understanding that we pass through as our intellect grows. They are remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating. He laid these out in his famous Bloom's Taxonomy. Bloom's taxonomy is a hierarchical arrangement of six cognitive processing abilities and educational objectives that range from simple to complex and concrete to abstract. In addition to identifying the cognitive abilities at each level of understanding, the taxonomy also includes describing the affective and psychomotor process that are involved at each level.

Table 1.0 People, Process, Technology Bloom’s Taxonomy

	People	Process	Technologies
	Rotational Replacement	Talent & Development Matrix	Soft & Hard Skill Training
Remembering	Know the define concepts of rotational replacement to refresh the culture and filling the development gap.	Increasing problem solving skills on each individu	The rapid advancement of technologies makes it very possible to simplify work.
Understanding	Usually it's followed by promoting the individual grade, but it can be also lateral grade or position	Each activity has a different level difficulty and a different way of solving it.	The difference in the system or similar aspects between the existing equipment and the new one.
Applying	Find the best position for employees to get new challenge, assignment, and wider helicopter view to support the business strategy.	Doing webinar and FAQ session to monitorized how far the participant understanding.	Training about tools and equipments by presenting from expert of those principal company.
Analyzing	Mind the gap between before and after those employees running those position. Is that any difference or not.	Analyze and implement the solution on the same problems.	Use the tools and equipments to know the pro’s & contra’s.
Evaluating	Monitoring by the people review forum	Increase the competencies between the before and after filling the development matrix. Proven by the difference on the organization that more efficient or not	There will be a significant difference on the result.
Creating	create or modify new key performance indicator to support business strategy even more.	Planning developpment matrix as a routine due to correlation on employee needs.	Doing refreshment to each employee and discuss on possibilities and problem solving that they will do.

AHP Methods

The use of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is not limited to governmental or private institutions; it can also be applied to individual needs (Kurniasari, 2023), especially for research related to policy-making or the formulation of strategic priorities. AHP is reliable because it structures priorities from various options that have been decomposed (structured) into criteria, making the establishment of priorities based on a structured (hierarchical) and rational process. Essentially, AHP helps to solve complex problems by creating a hierarchy of criteria, which are subjectively evaluated by stakeholders, and then drawing various considerations to develop weights or priorities (Saaty, 1995). AHP simplifies the problems by creating a clear hierarchical structure to assess priorities and make choices between alternatives (Saaty, 1990).

People vs Process vs Technology

From the survey results, a priority ranking for the three pillars of people development at PT Pertamina EP was established. Utilizing a calculation method based on the Business Performance Management Singapore (BPMSG) framework, it was determined that among the three main pillars — People, Process, and Technology — People has the most significant impact on people development. This finding underscores the importance of focusing on human resources and their development as a critical factor in enhancing overall organizational performance and effectiveness. Prioritizing the People pillar aligns with the understanding that investing in

the growth, skills, and well-being of employees leads to more substantial and positive outcomes for both individuals and the company as a whole (Woods, 1993).

When comparing People vs. Process, the People pillar has a higher impact, scoring 8 out of 9. Meanwhile, in the comparison between People and Technology, People is found to have an even greater impact, with a score of 7 out of 9. As for Process vs. Technology, the audience prefers Process as having a more significant impact than Technology in People Development. These findings highlight the hierarchy of influence among the pillars, with People at the forefront, followed by Process, and then Technology. This underscores the perception that while technology is essential, the human element and how processes are managed play a more critical role in the development of a company's workforce.

With a Consistency Ratio (CR) of 8%, it's confirmed that the People pillar is very much needed and is the most important pillar in People Development. This indicates that the assessment results are consistent and reliable, reinforcing the importance of focusing on the development of individuals within the organization. A CR within an acceptable range (typically 10% or less) suggests that the judgements made in the analysis are coherent and reflect a well-considered prioritization of the People pillar over Process and Technology in contributing to People Development.

70 : 20 : 10 Learning Model

It is a popular framework used to understand and support learning and development within organizations. It proposes that individuals obtain knowledge, skills, and abilities in their roles through the following mix : 70% from On-the-Job Experiences, 20% from Social Learning. Implementing the 70:20:10 model typically involves more than just providing resources or setting up training programs. It requires cultural changes where learning is integrated into the daily workflows, social interactions are encouraged and facilitated, and formal training supports and reinforces the learning happening through other means. This model is widely respected for its holistic approach to development, fostering environments where people continually learn and grow from their everyday experiences and interactions. (Blackman, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Since every pillars have some key factors with it own purpose, but it have the most effectiveness on people development. And on this research every factors combining as a new conceptual framework as below :

Table 2.0 New People Development Conceptual Framework

As we already know, people development at Pertamina is built upon three main pillars: People, Process, and Technology. Each of these pillars contains several key factors. People pillar with Job Rotational Replacement as main aspect, Process pillar with Talent Matrix Development as main aspect, and Technologies pillar with Soft & Hard Skill Training as main aspect. It also change the framework that become more efficient and applicable.

RECOMMENDATION

To achieve and maintain the effectiveness of the people development implemented by a company, several steps need to be taken, including: Identifying resources, which in this context refers to the employees at PT Pertamina EP – Sangatta Field. ; Flow of Process, A structured process is required to implement the newly created framework. The step-by-step approach should align with the company's SOP; Flow of Information, Information sources are needed to both implement and monitor the results of this new framework. ; Change Management, One or more change management initiatives need to be established, serving as a tool and source of information for the implementation of the new framework. ; Person in Charge, After determining the change management approach, the next step is to identify the individuals involved.

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